

Manual for Developing Final-Year Projects in Communication, Advertising and Public Relations

Abstract

This guide aims to orient students in the field of Social Sciences, especially those in Communication studies, in the development of their final university academic project. Regardless of its specific format, the final project is usually conceived as a culminating and independent piece of work through which students demonstrate their academic development, critical thinking, research skills and professional readiness. Its main purpose is to show that students can apply, in an integrated and coherent way, the knowledge, competencies and learning outcomes acquired throughout their university studies. Although each university, department and study programme establish its own requirements, assessment criteria, style guidelines and supervision procedures, there are a series of theoretical and practical principles that are usually shared across final undergraduate projects. For this reason, this document may be used as a practical guide to support students during the planning, development and completion of their project, as well as to address many of the doubts and concerns that may arise during the process.

Keywords:

Social Sciences; Communication Studies; Final-Year Project; Research Skills; Academic Development; Bachelor's Final Project; End-of-Degree Project; Project; Research Methodologies.

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The Final Project in Brief

In the fields of Communication, Advertising and Public Relations, the final project is particularly significant, as it requires the practical application of theories, approaches and models specific to the discipline, as well as the development of well-founded creative, professional and communication strategies. At the same time, it demands methodological rigor, analytical ability and critical thinking. In this sense, the final project should not be understood merely as an academic or administrative requirement, but rather as an integrative learning experience through which students demonstrate their ability to research, analyze, argue and synthesize the knowledge acquired throughout their university studies in relation to a specialized topic within their field.

The final project should represent the academic culmination of the degree and offer students the opportunity to explore in greater depth a topic, research line or

professional area in which they may wish to specialize in the future. It may also provide a means of presenting their profile to the professional sector, whether through the design of an applied project, an entrepreneurial proposal, a viable communication intervention or a high-quality research project that may be included in institutional repositories and, eventually, serve as a reference for future research.

In practice, however, the development of the final project can become a complex and, at times, discouraging process. This is partly because it often coincides with a particularly demanding final year, during which students must combine its completion with professional placements, other courses, career-oriented activities and the transition towards the labor market or postgraduate study. This accumulation of responsibilities may lead to procrastination, a lack of continuity in the work process and even the partial abandonment of the project. For this reason, this guide is conceived as a brief, practical and orientated resource. Its purpose is to provide a set of key principles to help students plan and develop their final project in an organized way, maintain a consistent working routine, avoid common obstacles and address some of the most frequent questions that tend to arise throughout the different stages of the process.

Choosing the Topic and Project Format

The choice of topic is one of the most important decisions in the development of the final academic project. An appropriate initial choice can play a decisive role in ensuring that the process is not perceived merely as a compulsory requirement, but rather as an academic, intellectual and professional opportunity. For this reason, the selected topic should, as far as possible, be connected to students' academic interests, personal concerns and short- or medium-term professional aspirations. This connection encourages sustained engagement with the project and allows the time devoted to its development to be understood as an investment in knowledge, specialization and skills development.

The choice of topic is therefore a critical first step. In addition to being related to the student's future professional orientation, the topic should be stimulating, relevant and sufficiently significant within the disciplinary field. The final project should not be limited to a descriptive reproduction of what other authors have already stated. Rather, it should aim to formulate a meaningful question, adopt a specific perspective, analyze a relevant case, propose an applied solution or contribute appropriately to the academic level of an undergraduate project. For this reason, it is highly advisable to conduct an initial exploratory review to identify previous research, related academic work, theoretical references, case studies and professional or research trends connected to the chosen area. This preliminary review helps assess the originality, relevance and suitability of the topic, as well as its alignment with the objectives of the degree programme.

Another fundamental aspect is the feasibility of the project. Before making a final decision, students should consider whether they will be able to access the necessary data, documents, sources, cases, participants or materials; whether the proposed objectives are achievable; whether the available time is sufficient; and whether they have the methodological, technical and analytical skills required to address the topic effectively. At this initial stage, the role of the project supervisor is

particularly important, as they can guide students in defining the topic, formulating the objectives and, above all, delimiting the scope of the work.

Delimiting the topic is one of the most complex tasks, especially in research-based projects. Students often propose topics that are excessively broad and more appropriate for a doctoral thesis or a long-term research programme than for an undergraduate final project. In this sense, the idea that “less is more” has clear methodological relevance. A well-delimited topic makes it possible to formulate more precise objectives, construct a more coherent theoretical framework, select an appropriate methodology and avoid superficial generalizations.

To delimit a topic means to define clearly what will be studied, from which perspective, over what period, in which context and using which materials or cases. For example, if a student wishes to analyze the evolution of brand storytelling, it would be difficult to address the phenomenon in its entirety. A more rigorous approach would be to focus on a specific sector, a particular brand, a defined country or a limited period. The student could also propose a comparative analysis of campaigns, agencies, platforms, discourses or communication strategies. Similarly, the project could examine how certain organizations apply brand storytelling in digital, audiovisual or transmedia contexts.

A final project becomes more rigorous when the object of study is delimited conceptually, temporally, geographically and methodologically. This delimitation does not weaken the project; rather, it strengthens it, because it allows for deeper analysis, better justification of methodological decisions and more robust conclusions. By contrast, an excessively broad approach often leads to imprecise results, weakly supported claims and superficial analysis. It may also generate frustration for students, who find themselves facing an object of study that is too extensive for the time, resources and academic level expected of an undergraduate project.

The degree of freedom to choose the topic, supervisor and project format will depend on each university, faculty and degree programme. In some programmes, especially those with a strong professional orientation, students may choose between a research-based format and a professional or applied format. This distinction is particularly common in fields such as Communication, Advertising, Public Relations and Journalism, where the final project may take different forms depending on the learning objectives of the programme.

In the research-based format, the project is usually structured around a research question, objectives, a theoretical framework, a methodology, an analysis of results and conclusions. In contrast, in the professional or applied format, the project may consist of the design of an advertising campaign, a communication plan, a transmedia strategy, a corporate visual identity manual, an event proposal, an audiovisual project, an entrepreneurial plan, the conceptual creation of an agency, the development of a brand or any other proposal linked to professional practice. In these cases, the written component usually takes the form of a justificatory, technical and reflective report, explaining the foundations, objectives, strategic decisions, work processes, references and evaluation criteria of the project developed.

1. **Personal interest and motivation.** What topics genuinely interest me within my field of study or within the professional sector I wish to enter?

2. **Academic and professional relevance.** Is the topic connected to current debates, emerging trends, professional needs or relevant issues within my discipline?
3. **State of the art.** What has already been researched or developed on this topic? Which aspects remain insufficiently explored?
4. **Originality and contribution.** Can my project offer a distinctive perspective, a relevant case study, an applied proposal, an update to existing knowledge or a solution to a specific problem?
5. **Feasibility.** Do I have access to the necessary data, sources, materials, cases or participants? Do I have the time, resources and skills required to develop the project rigorously?
6. **Delimitation.** Have I clearly defined what is included and what is excluded from the project? Have I adequately limited the period of analysis, context, corpus, media, sample, sector or target audience?
7. **Applicability and impact.** Can the topic be useful in real-world contexts, contribute to professional practice, generate transferable knowledge or serve as a starting point for future research?

Format, Structure and Length

The format of the final project usually follows an academic template established by each university, faculty or degree programme. This template may include guidelines concerning the organization of the document, citation style, font, margins, line spacing, page numbering, the presentation of tables and figures, as well as other formal requirements. It is therefore essential to consult and strictly follow the specific regulations of the institution before beginning the final drafting process. Although the structure of the project may vary depending on the university, discipline, chosen format and assessment requirements, there are several sections that commonly appear in undergraduate final projects. The most frequent are the following:

- Academic title page.
- Abstract and keywords, in the languages required by each university.
- Table of contents.
- Introduction.
- Objectives and, where appropriate, hypotheses or research questions.
- Methodology.
- Theoretical framework or literature review.
- Results, analysis, case study or development of the practical project.
- Conclusions.
- Bibliography or reference list.
- Appendices, where necessary.

As regards the minimum or maximum length of the project, this will depend on the academic regulations in force at each university, faculty or degree programme. Some institutions establish strict word or page limits, while others provide indicative ranges adapted to the nature of the project. In all cases, the length should be consistent with the objectives, methodology and scope of the work, avoiding both insufficient argumentation and the accumulation of irrelevant information.

The following sections will explain the function of each of these components in greater detail, with the aim of facilitating their understanding and providing clear guidance for the development of the final project.

The Introduction

The introduction plays an essential role in the final academic project, as it contextualizes the topic, presents the object of study and situates the line of work from which the research or professional project will be approached. The same phenomenon can be analyzed from multiple disciplines, theoretical approaches and methodological perspectives; for this reason, the introduction should clearly establish the starting point of the project, its specific focus and the reasons why the topic is worth addressing.

Although its length and configuration may vary depending on the regulations of each university or degree programme, the introduction should not be understood as a merely preliminary section or as a superficial presentation of the topic. Its function is to guide the reader, justify the academic and professional relevance of the project and establish the foundations on which the rest of the work will be developed. In some cases, a brief personal justification for the choice of topic may also be included, if it is written in an academic tone and connected to the student's educational background, research interests or professional aspirations.

Once the topic has been presented and contextualized, the introduction should explicitly state the objectives of the project, usually through one general objective and several specific objectives. In research-based projects, a research question may also be formulated, understood as the central question that guides the study and structures the subsequent analysis. In projects whose nature requires it, one or more hypotheses may also be proposed, if they are clearly formulated, testable and coherent with the objectives and methodology.

Fried et al. (2019) argue that an effective introduction in a research paper should capture the reader's interest, serve as a roadmap for the rest of the document and present the research questions that will be addressed in the following sections. In this sense, the introduction explains the starting point of the project—the topic to be investigated, the problem to be analyzed, the need to be addressed or the project to be developed—, argues for its importance and justifies its relevance within the corresponding academic or professional field.

The introduction may also include, towards the end, a brief description of the structure of the document. This description allows the reader to anticipate the development of the project and facilitates an understanding of its internal organization. For example, it may indicate that the first chapter reviews the existing literature on the topic, the second develops the methodological framework, the third presents the results or practical case, and the final section discusses the conclusions. This initial mapping provides the reader with a clear overview of the content and internal logic of the project.

A rigorous introduction should clearly present the problem statement, the objectives and, where appropriate, the hypotheses or research questions. These elements constitute the conceptual and methodological basis of the work, as they

provide direction, coherence and delimitation to the project. It is also advisable to indicate the scope of the study, specifying its temporal, geographical, thematic, conceptual or empirical limits. Delimiting the project means clarifying what is included, what is excluded and from which perspective the object of study will be approached.

Generally, an introduction should:

1. Present the central topic and contextualize it within its academic or professional field.
2. Justify the relevance of the project through an initial discussion of the problem, need, opportunity or knowledge gap.
3. Formulate the research question, when the project is research-based.
4. Present the general objective and the specific objectives.
5. State the hypotheses, if required by the nature of the study.
6. Delimit the scope of the project, specifying which aspects are included and which are excluded.
7. Briefly anticipate the methodological approach, although this will be developed in greater depth in the corresponding section.
8. Provide a concise overview of the structure of the document.
9. Include, where appropriate, a brief academic, professional or personal justification for the choice of topic.

As in the rest of the project, the introduction should be written in formal language that is precise and consistent with the discipline. It is advisable to use an academic style, preferably in the present or past tense, with a predominance of the active voice and avoiding colloquial expressions, vague statements, unsupported value judgements or generalizations based on personal perceptions. The writing should be clear, grammatically correct and terminologically appropriate to the field of study.

It is also essential to avoid presenting unsupported claims as self-evident. Students should distinguish between opinions, intuitions, data, arguments and evidence. In academic work, relevant claims should be supported by sources, studies, reports, empirical data or properly grounded reasoning. Likewise, the introduction should not anticipate definitive conclusions or assume results before the analysis has been carried out.

The following examples illustrate weak formulations and possible more rigorous alternatives:

1. Unsupported opinions

✗ *Everyone knows that transmedia is the future.*

✓ *Several recent studies have identified the growing relevance of transmedia strategies in brand communication planning, particularly in digital and multiplatform environments (Author, year).*

✗ *Researchers who are now experts in artificial intelligence are experts because they are not really experts in anything.*

✓ *Some studies on academic trends have examined how certain researchers redirect their lines of work towards emerging areas, such as artificial intelligence, in response to changes in scientific, technological and professional agendas (Author, year).*

2. Overgeneralizations

✗ *Social media are addictive.*

✓ *Certain studies have identified patterns of problematic social media use among specific segments of young people, particularly in relation to platforms characterized by high-frequency visual and social interaction (Author, year).*

3. Vague or biased justifications

✗ *Everyone considers this topic important.*

✓ *The scarcity of recent studies on this phenomenon in the context of small and medium-sized enterprises justifies the relevance of analysing its impact on strategic communication planning (Author, year).*

✗ *People who consider themselves leaders after taking a leadership course are not real leaders.*

✓ *The literature on organizational leadership distinguishes between training in managerial competencies and the effective recognition of leadership by work teams, which makes it possible to analyze the gap between self-perceived leadership and its internal legitimation (Author, year).*

4. Excessively broad approaches

✗ *We will analyze digital fashion communication in Spain.*

✓ *This project will analyze the use of TikTok as a communication channel for sustainable fashion brands based in Madrid during 2026.*

5. Premature conclusions or value judgements

✗ *We will demonstrate that campaign X failed.*

✓ *The effectiveness of campaign X will be evaluated based on engagement, reach and alignment with the previously defined communication objectives.*

Objectives and Hypotheses

Research objectives are one of the central components of any academic project, as they define what the study intends to achieve, delimit its scope and guide theoretical, methodological and analytical decisions in a coherent way. In general terms, objectives transform a research problem, question or need into specific, observable and assessable goals. In this regard, Bailey and Doody (2016) argue that a research objective makes it possible to turn a relevant issue into a concrete goal that can be achieved and evaluated throughout the study.

Objectives should be formulated clearly, precisely and coherently in relation to the problem statement, research question, methodology and expected outcomes. It is not enough to state that the project aims to “study” or “discuss” a topic. Instead, it is necessary to define exactly which dimension of the phenomenon will be analysed, for what purpose, in relation to which corpus, sample, context or case, and through which methodological approach.

One of the most common classifications of objectives is hierarchical. Hernández Sampieri et al. (2016) distinguish between the general objective, which expresses the main purpose of the study, and the specific objectives, which break that purpose down into concrete, organised and measurable actions. The general objective acts as the central axis of the project, while the specific objectives make it possible to operationalise it and organise the different stages of the work.

For example:

General objective (G.O.): To analyse the influence of social media on adolescents' self-esteem through proprioception and resilience (Freire-Sánchez et al., 2024).

Specific objectives (S.O.):

1. To identify the daily amount of time spent using social media.
2. To assess the self-esteem levels of the adolescent participants.
3. To correlate social media use with the proprioception and resilience of these adolescents.

From another perspective, Kerlinger and Lee (2002), in their work on research methods in the social sciences, classify objectives according to their function within the study. Based on this logic, several types of objectives can be distinguished:

Descriptive objectives. These seek to characterise a phenomenon, identify its main features or describe its components. For example: to describe the elements that characterise the playlists of brand soundtracks on Spotify (Fitó Carreras et al., 2024).

Correlational objectives. These aim to analyse the relationship between two or more variables, without necessarily establishing a causal relationship. For example: to examine the relationship between work-related stress and the perceived incompetence of a direct supervisor.

Explanatory objectives. These seek to identify causes, effects or mechanisms that explain a phenomenon. For example: to determine whether a specific management method reduces talent turnover in an organisation.

Exploratory objectives. These are used when the topic has been insufficiently studied or when the project aims to provide an initial approach to an emerging phenomenon. For example: to explore older adults' perceptions of the use of artificial intelligence in digital services.

When writing objectives, vague, generic or excessively broad formulations should be avoided. Expressions such as "to study digital communication", "to analyse social media" or "to understand contemporary advertising" are insufficient unless the focus, context, period, sample or method is clearly specified. As far as possible, and always in accordance with the nature of the project, objectives should follow the S.M.A.R.T. criterion: they should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time bound. This does not mean that all objectives must follow a quantitative logic, but rather that they should be realistically and assessably addressed within the limits of the project.

Recommendations for Writing Objectives

1. Use infinitive verbs that express observable and academically appropriate actions, such as to analyse, to describe, to assess, to compare, to identify, to interpret, to design, to examine or to classify.
2. Ensure coherence between the objectives and the methodology. An objective that involves measuring, quantifying or correlating variables will require appropriate quantitative techniques and instruments; by contrast, an objective aimed at exploring, interpreting or understanding a phenomenon may be addressed through qualitative techniques.
3. Formulate realistic objectives in relation to the available time, resources, access to data or sources and the student's methodological skills.
4. Ensure that the specific objectives contribute directly to the achievement of the general objective. They should not function as independent tasks or introduce lines of work unrelated to the main purpose of the project.
5. Avoid objectives that are overly ambitious, abstract or impossible to verify. An undergraduate final project should be rigorous, but also feasible and proportionate to its academic level.

Examples of Objectives in Advertising and Public Relations Projects

Example 1

To identify and categorise the discursive strategies used by three fast-fashion brands in their post-crisis communications between 2020 and 2024, through a content analysis of 300 Twitter/X posts supported by Atlas.ti software.

Example 2

To identify and quantify the impact of emotional branding on the tourist perception of the Gràcia district in Barcelona, through 300 surveys conducted with visitors during July and August 2025 and a semiotic analysis of 10 municipal campaigns developed between 2019 and 2024, to design a validated model of brand attributes.

Example 3

To analyse how three Barcelona-based brands —Casa Amatller, Cacaolat and Bultaco— integrate modernist heritage into their digital brand storytelling between 2020 and 2025, by classifying narrative strategies through a content analysis of 150 Instagram posts and interviews with five cultural managers during the second half of 2025.

Example of Objective Reformulation

✗ *To study Nike's storytelling.*

✓ *To analyse the use of heroic archetypes in five Nike advertising campaigns developed between 2020 and 2024 through visual semiotic analysis.*

The second formulation is more appropriate because it delimits the object of study, specifies the corpus, establishes a concrete period and indicates the methodological approach to be used.

Hypotheses

Hypotheses are provisional, grounded and testable propositions that anticipate a possible relationship between variables. Their function is to guide the research process and offer a tentative answer to the research question. A hypothesis should not be formulated intuitively or based solely on personal opinions; rather, it should derive from the theoretical framework, the literature review and the available empirical background. In academic terms, hypotheses are statements that may be confirmed, qualified or rejected through the development of the research. To be useful, they must be clear, specific, coherent with the objectives and formulated in such a way that they can be tested through the selected methodology. For example: *There is a significant positive relationship between a brand's posting frequency on Instagram and the level of user engagement.*

The formulation of hypotheses is particularly relevant in quantitative, correlational, explanatory or experimental research, although hypotheses may also appear in some mixed-methods studies. In qualitative or exploratory projects, by contrast, it is more common to work with research questions, initial assumptions or guiding propositions, without necessarily formulating closed hypotheses.

When formulating a hypothesis, it is advisable to identify the variables involved and the expected relationship between them. The independent variable is the explanatory, predictor or antecedent factor; that is, the element that is selected, manipulated or considered as a possible cause or influence. The dependent variable is the outcome, effect or response that is observed, analysed or measured. Losh (2017) explains that dependent variables may also be referred to as outcome, response or criterion variables, while independent variables may be understood as explanatory or predictor variables. For example, in the hypothesis *posting frequency on Instagram has a positive influence on user engagement*, posting frequency would be the independent variable, while user engagement would be the dependent variable.

Recommendations for Formulating Hypotheses

1. Derive the hypothesis from the theoretical framework and the state of the art.
2. Formulate it clearly, specifically and testably.
3. Identify the main variables and the expected relationship between them.
4. Avoid absolute, ambiguous or unverifiable statements.
5. Ensure coherence between the hypothesis, the objectives and the methodology.
6. Do not anticipate conclusions as if they had already been demonstrated.

The following table presents several basic examples of independent and dependent variables. These examples illustrate the relationship between an explanatory or predictor factor and an observable or measurable outcome.

Table 1. Examples of Independent and Dependent Variables

Independent variable	Dependent variable
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Cause, explanatory factor or element being categorised	Effect, consequence or observed outcome
Hours of study	Exam grade
Frequency of social media posts	Engagement rate
Visibility of sustainability certifications	Purchase intention
Perceived authenticity of the brand narrative	Brand trust

Source: author's own elaboration.

The following example shows how an independent variable and a dependent variable may be incorporated into the formulation of a hypothesis:

Hypothesis:

Brands that incorporate complex female antihero characters into their narratives increase female audience identification compared with brands that rely on traditional heroine figures.

Variables:

Independent variable: type of character archetype used in the brand narrative—complex antiheroine versus traditional heroine—.

Dependent variable: level of female audience identification, measured through the percentage of women who state that they feel represented by those characters.

An appropriate way to identify independent variables for qualitative analysis is to draw on the specialized literature, established theoretical models or the canonical features that define a genre, professional practice or field of study. For example, Freire-Sánchez and Vidal-Mestre (2025) analyze the gameplay mechanics of video games inspired by the work of H. P. Lovecraft based on the characteristics of cosmic horror defined by Lovecraft himself. This type of approach makes it possible to transform theoretical concepts into analytical categories that can be applied to specific case studies.

Before formulating a hypothesis, it is essential to conduct a literature review or, at least, a systematic examination of the state of the art. Otherwise, there is a risk of proposing hypotheses that are weakly grounded, excessively intuitive, obvious or already addressed by previous research. For example, in 2025 it would be of limited relevance to ask whether video games can be considered art, since academic research has for decades approached video games as a form of digital culture, interactive design and contemporary artistic expression. Such a question would contribute little to existing knowledge unless it were reformulated from a more specific, current and problematized perspective.

Table 2. Definition, Focus and Function of Research Questions, Objectives and Hypotheses

Concept	Focus	Function	Criteria and recommendations	What should be avoided
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Research question	What the project aims to answer	To guide the study based on an initial question, problem or reflection that motivates the research	It should include, where necessary, temporal, spatial, thematic or empirical delimitation. It should lead to a concrete and feasible analysis	Obvious questions that do not require research. Questions that cannot be answered. Categorical or overly binary formulations. Excessively broad questions, such as “What is branding?”. Vague terms such as “impact”, “relationship” or “influence” if they are not clearly defined
Objectives	What the project aims to achieve	To delimit, organize and guide the development of the project	They should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound where possible. Clear action verbs should be used, such as identify, compare, analyze, assess, quantify, design or classify. They should specify the what, the how and the context of the study	Vague formulations such as “to study”, “to observe” or “to understand” if they are not specified. Objectives that are not measurable, are disproportionate or are not directly aligned with the methodology
Hypothesis	What the project expects to test	To anticipate a possible relationship between variables and subject it to examination	They should be theoretically grounded and testable through data, analysis or evidence. If variables are used, they should be clearly defined and logically connected to the hypothesis	Hypotheses without theoretical grounding, with undefined variables or that cannot be tested. Hypotheses already superseded by the literature. Overly obvious statements, such as “social media influence young people”

Source: author's own elaboration.

The following example, focused on the **Marvel Cinematic Universe** (MCU), illustrates the relationship between a research question, a general objective, specific objectives and hypotheses.

Research question:

How have transmedia world-building resources, multiplatform canon management and fandom participation contributed to the narrative expansion of the Marvel Cinematic Universe between 2008 and 2024?

General objective:

To explain the logic of transmedia expansion in the Marvel Cinematic Universe between 2008 and 2024 through an integrated analysis of its narrative strategies, multiplatform canonical coherence and interaction with fandom.

Specific objectives:

S.O.1. To identify the five most recurrent world-building resources across films, comics and Disney+ series, classifying them by frequency through a content analysis of 20 products.

S.O.2. To assess canonical coherence in crossover events linked to key characters and franchises, such as Avengers and Spider-Man, through a

comparative analysis of 10 major story arcs and interviews or consultations with three experts.

S.O.3. To quantify fandom participation in the creation of derivative content, such as fan fiction and Reddit theories, through the analysis of 200 samples and the identification of possible links with official creative decisions between 2019 and 2023.

Main hypothesis:

There is a positive and significant relationship between the frequency of transmedia content releases in the Marvel Cinematic Universe and the volume of social media conversation about the franchise.

Secondary hypothesis:

There is a significant positive correlation between the combined release of transmedia products—films and series—and the increase in daily mentions on Twitter/X during the seven days following each release.

It is important to note that not all final projects require formal hypotheses. In exploratory, descriptive or qualitative studies, it may be more appropriate to work with research questions, objectives or guiding propositions. For example, a case study aimed at describing the implementation of a communication campaign or the design of a Public Relations plan may not require hypotheses to be tested. In such cases, the project should clearly justify that it is structured around research questions and objectives, and that hypotheses are not included due to the nature, approach and scope of the study.

Methodological Design or Methodology

The methodological design is the roadmap that explains how the research will be conducted to achieve the stated objectives and answer the research question. In a final project in Communication, Advertising or Public Relations, this section should clearly justify the methodological approach adopted—quantitative, qualitative or mixed—, the data collection techniques, the instruments used, the analytical procedure and, where applicable, the ethical considerations of the study.

If the introduction addresses the what, why and for what purpose of the project, the methodology addresses the how. In other words, this section should explain how the data or information required to address the research problem will be obtained, organized, analyzed and interpreted. It is therefore not enough to list techniques or tools: students must justify why these have been selected and how they are suited to the object of study, the objectives and the type of results expected.

The choice of methodological approach should be directly linked to the nature of the research problem. For example, if the objective is to measure the effectiveness of a campaign through numerical indicators, a quantitative design may be more appropriate. By contrast, if the aim is to understand opinions, perceptions, discourses or experiences in depth, a qualitative approach may be more suitable (Del Olmo y Freire, 2022). Mixed methods are also common when the aim is to combine the robustness of quantitative data with the interpretive depth of qualitative data. For

example, Fitó-Carreras et al. (2024) combined surveys of large groups of students from different universities with content analysis to assess Communication students' perceptions of linear radio. Similarly, Vidal-Mestre et al. (2023) integrated quantitative and qualitative data in their analysis of the main YouTube channels run by content creators in the film sector.

In general terms, methodological approaches may be classified as follows:

Quantitative research is oriented towards the analysis of measurable variables and usually follows a deductive logic. It typically begins with hypotheses that are tested through numerical data and statistical procedures (Hernández-Sampieri & Mendoza, 2018). This approach uses techniques such as surveys with closed-ended questions, experiments, structured observations or quantified content analysis. Its main features include the prior definition of variables, the use of representative or justified samples, the reliability and validity of instruments, and the application of statistical procedures. A quantitative project could consist, for example, of conducting a survey with a specific sample of participants to measure attitudes towards an advertising campaign and subsequently analyzing the data with statistical software.

Qualitative research is oriented towards an in-depth understanding of social, cultural or communicative phenomena in their natural context. Unlike quantitative designs, it does not necessarily begin with fixed hypotheses, but rather seeks to identify meanings, motivations, experiences, discourses or interpretive patterns (Aspers & Corte, 2019). This approach uses flexible techniques, such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, participant or non-participant observation, discourse analysis, semiotic analysis or qualitative content analysis. In this type of research, direct engagement with the subjects, texts, contexts or communities analyzed is fundamental. The analysis often produces thematic categories, complex interpretations or explanatory models derived from the research process itself. Qualitative research usually works with smaller but information-rich samples and may continue until theoretical saturation is reached. Its main value lies in contextual depth and in its capacity to address questions concerning the how and why of social phenomena.

Mixed methodology combines quantitative and qualitative procedures within the same design. It may be developed in different ways: by first collecting quantitative data and then explaining them through qualitative techniques, or by beginning with an exploratory qualitative phase that is later expanded or tested through quantitative data. This approach enriches the research by allowing statistical patterns to be contrasted with in-depth interpretations, or by complementing the analysis of general trends with an understanding of particular contexts, discourses and experiences.

To determine which methodology is most appropriate, students should begin with the objectives of the project. If the aim is to measure the prevalence of a phenomenon, test hypotheses, generalize results or parameterize a specific case, a quantitative approach is usually selected. If the purpose is to interpret experiences, analyze discourses, understand meanings, study specific cases or generate knowledge from contexts, a qualitative

methodology is usually more appropriate. When both purposes are relevant, a mixed-methods design may be adopted.

The methodology section should specify at least the following elements: the methodological approach, the universe or population under study, the sample size and selection criteria, the type of sampling used —random, purposive, convenience, theoretical, among others—, the data collection techniques, the specific instruments —questionnaires, interview guides, analysis sheets, coding matrices—, the data collection procedure and the analytical method. It should also indicate whether specialized software has been used, such as statistical programmes, databases, spreadsheets, reference managers, qualitative analysis tools or content analysis software. If the research involves interviews, surveys, observation of people, sensitive data or the processing of personal information, the ethical safeguards adopted must be explained, such as informed consent, data anonymization or approval by an ethics committee, where applicable.

Common Qualitative Methods in Communication, Advertising & PR

There are numerous qualitative methods, some of which are more closely associated with disciplines such as Philosophy, Philology, Anthropology, Sociology or Fine Arts. In the fields of Communication, Advertising and Public Relations, some of the most common methods are the following:

In-depth interviews

These are semi-structured conversations with individuals relevant to the object of study, such as industry experts, the target audience of a campaign, communication managers, community managers, communication directors, journalists, content creators or specialized professionals. Their purpose is to obtain perceptions, experiences, assessments or interpretations of the phenomenon under analysis (Knott et al., 2022). They require a flexible guide organized around thematic blocks, allowing the researcher to explore nuances and aspects not initially anticipated. To use interview content in an academic project, informed consent must be obtained from the interviewees.

Focus groups

These are group sessions in which a moderator guides the discussion around a specific topic. They may be used, for example, to analyze the reception of a controversial advertisement, perceptions of a brand, the assessment of an institutional campaign or interpretations of a corporate crisis. Focus groups are useful for observing interactions, agreements, disagreements and collectively constructed meanings. However, they require effective moderation to prevent the discussion from becoming polarized or dominated by a small number of participants. In Freire-Sánchez et al. (2023), for instance, several focus groups were conducted to assess the introduction of anime into advertising campaigns aimed at Advertising students.

Participant or non-participant observation

This method makes it possible to analyze behaviors, practices, interactions or communicative contexts. In Public Relations, for example, it could be used to observe how attendees interact at a brand event. In political communication, it could be used to analyze the dynamics of attendees at a party rally, their reactions to spokespersons' speeches or the ways in which political narratives are staged. Participant observation involves the researcher's involvement in the observed context, whereas non-participant observation maintains an external position.

Discourse analysis or qualitative content analysis

This type of analysis is based on the systematic examination of texts, advertisements, social media posts, news items, speeches, campaigns, audiovisual pieces or other communicative materials. Its purpose is to interpret meanings, narrative structures, metaphors, discursive frames, symbolic representations or rhetorical strategies. It may draw on approaches such as critical discourse analysis, semiotics, narratology or thematic analysis. According to Lindgren et al. (2020), qualitative content analysis focuses on identifying, describing and interpreting the latent meanings and values present in narratives or texts through systematic processes of coding and categorization, which may be inductive or deductive.

Film and audiovisual analysis

This method studies how images, sounds, *mise-en-scène*, editing, narration and other expressive resources organize and communicate meanings in audiovisual works such as films, series, music videos, advertisements or digital content. Rose (2016) emphasizes the importance of analyzing visual materials by considering both their formal components and their cultural meanings. In this regard, audiovisual analysis can distinguish between form and content; Ordóñez (2018) differentiates between narration, understood as the way in which a story is told, and narrative, understood as what is being told.

Netnography or digital ethnography.

Netnography, or digital ethnography, involves the systematic observation of communities, practices and discourses in digital environments. In Advertising and Public Relations, it may be used to analyze how fans of a brand express themselves in online communities, how a collective identity is constructed around a campaign or how participatory practices emerge on social media. For example, Freire-Sánchez et al. (2024) conducted a digital ethnography of the fandom surrounding *Goncharov*, the non-existent film attributed to Scorsese, to understand how a fictional film became a global phenomenon from a simple meme. Previously, Freire and Vidal-Mestre (2022) conducted another digital ethnography to identify which characters were considered contemporary antiheroes by the global social media community; once the sample had been obtained, these characters were analyzed through independent variables extracted from a specialized literature review.

Developing the Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework is the section in which students demonstrate their knowledge of the theories, concepts, models, debates and previous findings related to the topic of the project. Its function is to provide the conceptual basis from which the results will be interpreted, or the development of the professional project will be justified. In Communication, Advertising and Public Relations, the theoretical framework should be clearly connected to the object of study, the objectives and the methodology, and should avoid becoming a disorganized accumulation of definitions or authors.

One of the fundamental components of the theoretical framework is the literature review. This review involves searching for, reading, selecting, analyzing and synthesizing relevant academic sources. The main sources should be articles published in scientific journals, specialized books, book chapters, research reports, doctoral theses or academically reliable documents. Not all sources have the same value: a rigorous theoretical framework should prioritize relevant, up-to-date academic literature that is directly related to the research problem.

It is advisable to begin the search in academic databases such as Web of Science, Scopus or Google Scholar. Specialized journals in the field of Communication may also be consulted, such as *Revista de Comunicación*, *Games and Culture*, *Revista Latina de Comunicación Social*, *Communication & Society*, *index.comunicación*, *Gráfica*, *Rotura*, *Fotocinema*, *Cuadernos.info*, *Palabra Clave*, *Critical Studies of Television*, *Radio Journal* or *Con A de Animación*, among others. In addition, it is necessary to consult and include classic literature and key references in the field when the topic requires it.

The literature review should be selective and relevant. The aim is not to include everything that has been published on a topic, but to identify the contributions that help to better understand the problem, define the key concepts, justify the research and build a solid basis for the analysis. For this reason, excessively general sections or content disconnected from the object of study should be avoided. If artificial intelligence-based tools or AI-assisted academic search engines, such as Consensus or SCl, are used, it is essential to review the original linked sources and verify that the cited articles support the ideas attributed to them.

The theoretical framework may be organized according to different criteria. In some cases, it is appropriate to structure it by themes or key variables. In others, especially when studying the evolution of a concept—for example, corporate purpose, reputation, storytelling or engagement—a chronological organization may be more suitable, as it allows the student to show how the academic or professional debate has evolved over time.

For example, if a project addresses transmedia storytelling in advertising, the theoretical framework could be organized into sections such as the following:

- a) concept and evolution of storytelling.
- b) origins and principles of transmedia narrative, including the contributions of Henry Jenkins and other relevant authors.
- c) audience participation and engagement in transmedia contexts.
- d) previous studies on brand transmedia campaigns, with attention to their findings, transformations and reception.

e) applicable communication theories, such as media convergence, participatory culture, mixed narratives or brand storytelling models.

After reviewing the literature, it is advisable to identify one or more theories, models or approaches that will serve as the direct conceptual support for the study. A project cannot analyze a phenomenon from every existing theory, as this would lead to an unmanageable, imprecise or incoherent analysis. For this reason, the theoretical framework usually performs a dual function: on the one hand, it reviews existing knowledge on the topic; on the other, it selects the specific theoretical perspective from which the analysis will be developed. For example, in a project on the effectiveness of campaigns based on user-generated content, models related to narrative persuasion, viral communication or audience participation could be adopted. The selected theories should be presented in sufficient detail, defining their central concepts and, where relevant, including empirical precedents for their application.

In some projects, the state of the art and the theoretical framework may be integrated or partially overlap. The state of the art focuses primarily on what has previously been researched on the topic, whereas the theoretical framework explains the concepts, theories or models through which the study will be approached. Although both dimensions may be developed together, it is important for the project to cover both: the review of previous studies and the definition of the theoretical perspective adopted.

The theoretical framework is also the appropriate place to define the key concepts of the project precisely. Terms such as engagement, transmedia branding, corporate reputation, storytelling, fandom, brand identity or strategic communication should be explained using authoritative sources, avoiding intuitive or ambiguous uses. This conceptual precision brings clarity, coherence and rigor to the project. The theoretical framework should be written in an organized, logical and progressive manner. It is advisable to divide it into thematic sections with clear subheadings, to develop each section through sustained argumentation and to close the main sections with a brief synthesis that connects the theory reviewed with the specific problem of the project. In this way, the theoretical framework not only demonstrates academic knowledge, but also fulfils a structural function: it supports methodological decisions, guides the analysis and sustains the interpretation of the results.

The theoretical framework should be supported by citations from the academic sources consulted. Including these references not only acknowledges the intellectual authorship of other researchers but also strengthens the argumentative solidity of the project and situates it within a broader academic conversation.

It is essential to avoid any form of plagiarism. Even when paraphrasing ideas, arguments, concepts or findings from other authors, students must cite them appropriately and respect the intellectual authorship of the content used. Paraphrasing does not mean simply replacing a few words with synonyms; rather, it involves reformulating an idea in one's own words while preserving its original meaning and properly attributing it to the relevant source. It is also advisable to work with a sufficiently diverse range of sources. A rigorous theoretical framework should combine classic studies, which provide the conceptual and theoretical foundations of the field, with recent research, preferably published within the last five to ten years, to

incorporate up-to-date debates, approaches and evidence. In particularly dynamic fields such as Communication, Advertising and Public Relations, it is essential to review recent literature that reflects sectoral transformations, emerging trends and current academic discussions.

For example, in 2026 it would not be appropriate to present virality or digital transformation as novel phenomena in themselves. Instead, it would be more relevant to analyze how these concepts have evolved, what new practices or problems they currently raise, and how they relate to the specific object of the project.

Although these terms are sometimes used interchangeably in academic work, there are important distinctions between the state of the art, the referential framework, the theoretical framework and the conceptual framework. Understanding these differences helps students construct a stronger, more coherent and more useful theoretical-analytical basis for their project. The following comparative table distinguishes the function, objectives, content and application of each approach. To maintain continuity with the section on objectives and hypotheses, the transmedia narrative universe of Marvel is used as an example.

Table 3. Differences between the Conceptual Framework, Theoretical Framework, Referential Framework and State of the Art

Element	Conceptual framework	Theoretical framework	Referential framework	State of the art
Purpose	It functions as an analytical glossary that defines and delimits the key concepts, categories and variables of the study. It usually derives from the theoretical framework and clarifies how the central terms will be understood within the project.	It brings together the theories, models and approaches that explain the phenomenon under study and guide the hypotheses, variables, methodology and interpretation of results. It is built from the literature review, but constitutes the student's own construction, providing the interpretive "lens" of the study. It may integrate the conceptual framework and the literature review.	It places the object of study within its historical, legal, cultural, social, institutional or professional context. It helps explain the external conditions surrounding the phenomenon analyzed.	It offers a critical synthesis of previous research, especially recent empirical studies, on the topic. It shows what has been studied, from which perspectives and with what results.
Objectives	To clarify analytical definitions and establish the operational meaning of the central concepts of the project.	To provide explanatory support, academic coherence and conceptual grounding for the study.	To contextualize the research within its real environment and explain the external factors that affect the phenomenon.	To identify gaps, trends, debates, areas of consensus and controversies in existing research.
Content	Key concepts, constructs, analytical categories and relationships between variables.	Theories, models, disciplinary approaches and relevant conceptual background.	Regulations, sectoral background, contextual data, historical evolution, institutional features or characteristics of the sector.	Scientific articles, theses, reports, projects and studies published in recent years.
Time scope	It may be relatively timeless, as long as the concepts remain useful and valid.	It depends on the validity of the theories; it may include both classic authors and recent contributions.	It may be historical or current, depending on the objectives of the project.	It prioritises recent research, usually published within the last five or ten years.

Example applied to Marvel's transmedia narrative universe	Concepts such as world-building, canon, cross-media, fandom, transmedia expansion or narrative continuity.	Theories such as cultural convergence (Jenkins, 2006), transmedia narratology (Scolari, 2013) and other models related to participatory culture and narrative franchises.	The history of Marvel comics, the evolution of the audiovisual industry, distribution platforms, the corporate structure of the franchise and intellectual property legislation.	A review of studies published between 2015 and 2025 on the Marvel Cinematic Universe, fan consumption, the franchise's transmedia strategies and fandom participation.
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Source: author's own elaboration.

Therefore, each student should decide which type of approach is most appropriate according to the chosen topic, the objectives of the project and the methodology adopted. Not all projects require these four sections to be developed separately. However, it is important to understand that, in most cases, a solid theoretical framework will need to be supported by a literature review and by a precise definition of the conceptual framework.

Case Study, Results Analysis or Practical Case

The case study, results analysis or development of a practical case is often one of the most relevant, original and significant parts of the final project. This section constitutes the core of the work, as it is where the selected methodology is applied in order to address the research problem, respond to the objectives and, where applicable, test the hypotheses or develop a professional proposal.

In the fields of Communication, Advertising and Public Relations, projects are frequently structured around the analysis of a specific case, such as a brand, company, institution, campaign, communicative situation, event, reputational crisis, digital strategy or communication project. In professionally oriented projects, this section may take the form of an applied proposal, such as a communication plan, an advertising campaign, a Public Relations strategy, a corporate visual identity manual, an entrepreneurial project or a communication intervention.

In this part of the project, students should present their results in an organized, coherent way that is aligned with the methodology. This may involve describing the case analyzed, presenting empirical findings, interpreting the data obtained, organizing analytical categories, comparing results or justifying the decisions made in the development of a practical project. In all cases, results should not be presented as a mere accumulation of information, but as an argued exposition that allows the reader to understand what has been found, how those findings were reached and how they relate to the objectives of the project.

Given the wide variety of possible case studies and practical projects, students are encouraged to consult institutional repositories of undergraduate and master's dissertations, as well as university digital libraries. Reviewing previous examples can help students understand different ways of organizing this section, while keeping in mind that each project must respond to its own object of study, methodology and academic regulations.

Conclusions

The conclusions should bring the project to a reasoned close and provide a clear response to the objectives initially proposed. They should not merely summarize previous sections, but should explain the main contributions of the project, whether to the state of the art, the research problem, the professional sector or the development of an applied proposal.

This section is more interpretive in nature than the rest of the project, although it must remain academically rigorous. In general, the conclusions are not expected to introduce new sources, citations or data that have not been previously addressed. Their main function is to assess the findings obtained, answer the research question, indicate whether the objectives have been achieved and, if hypotheses were formulated, explain whether they have been accepted, rejected or qualified based on the results.

The conclusions may also include a reflection on the limitations of the study. These limitations may relate to sample size, access to data, available time, corpus delimitation, methodological approach or the specific conditions of the case analyzed. Acknowledging limitations does not weaken the project; on the contrary, it demonstrates academic maturity and critical awareness of the actual scope of the research. Finally, it is advisable to identify future lines of research or possible practical applications. In a research-based project, these may include new questions, comparative cases, methodological extensions or theoretical perspectives that could be explored in future studies. In a professionally oriented project, they may include improvements, implementation phases, evaluation indicators, transfer possibilities or recommendations applicable to the sector.

About bibliography

The bibliography's section should include only the sources that have been consulted, used and cited throughout the project. References that do not appear in the body of the text, or sources that have not contributed directly to the development of the project, should not be included. Unless the university's regulations state otherwise, APA 7 is usually recommended in the field of Communication Sciences. This style provides specific criteria for in-text citations and for the final reference list, including books, book chapters, scientific articles, websites, reports, theses, audiovisual materials and other types of sources.

It is essential to ensure an exact correspondence between the citations included in the text and the references listed in the final bibliography. Every source cited in the body of the project must appear in the bibliography, and every reference included in the bibliography must have been cited in the text. References should also be presented consistently, arranged alphabetically and formatted accurately according to the chosen citation style. Students may consult updated APA 7 guides, as well as the author guidelines of scientific journals that use this citation system.

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